

Scelotes bipes

Silvery Dwarf Burrowing Skink

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

© L. Kemp

Group: Reptile

Size: 10 - 20 cm (total body length)

Distribution:

Endemic to the Republic of South Africa, Western Cape Province, ranging from Mossel Bay to near Saldanha Bay.

Importance:

This species is an important model for investigating limb reduction and genomic evolution in vertebrates. Within the genus *Scelotes*, it represents an intermediate limb development stage (forelimb digits = 0; hindlimb digits = 2), making it particularly valuable for comparative developmental and evolutionary studies. Its restricted distribution across distinct habitats and regions further enhances its utility as a model species for biogeographic and molecular ecology research.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 69.13 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 5.32 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Flye

Genome Length: 1.54 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.6% [Single: 98.4%, Duplicated: 1.2%]

BUSCO database: eukaryota

Assembly N50: 1032.76 kilobases

Contig number: 9 630

Sample Contributor contact details:

Dr. Zhongning Zhao
University of Free State
orochi19851020@yahoo.com

DIPLOMICS
CONNECTING RESEARCHERS & WORLD CLASS OMICS FACILITIES

Date Published: 2026-02-05

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18608497>

